

FACTSHEET Lecture 1

RMIS – Long-life learners version

OUTLINE

- 1. UNIFIED INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR RAW MATERIAL BACKSTORY**
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1. UNIFIED INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR RAW MATERIAL BACKSTORY

It is obvious that over time, any information loses its relevance for various reasons - due to changing factors in the external or internal environment, market situation, geopolitical changes etc. The information in the developed database is no exception and may also become obsolete over time. Another factor negatively affecting the relevance and completeness of information is the changing state of the raw material base, which also requires constant and prompt updating of the database. On the other hand, usually statistical tables have an update period equal to one year, which is an unacceptably long period in modern conditions, when the development of information technology and the widespread use of the global Internet, including in remote regions of the country, make it possible to update all the necessary information. At the same time, prompt updating is possible only if there is a centralized system for storing data on the state of the raw material base and the possibility of obtaining remote access to this system. Another prerequisite in favour of developing such a distributed system is the fact that the technical services of specific mines have complete, up-to-date and correct information about the state of the raw material base, the equipment and technologies used at the mine, and providing these services with access to the information system can solve the problem of data transmission speed and their relevance. According to a fully-fledged strategy for raw materials developed by the European Commission, which was outlined in the 2008 Communication entitled the Raw Materials Initiative and revised in February 2011 in a Communication, which further boosted the integration of raw material priorities in EU policies. EU trade policy is actively committed to ensuring that international raw materials markets operate in a free and transparent manner with smooth synergy between major policy drivers, and stakeholder (customer) groups through the Raw Materials (RM) value chain.

To implement this strategy, The RMIS (Raw Material Information System) was launched in 2015 to facilitate key information and knowledge needs of the European Commission and of the Member States on non-food, non-energy raw materials. It is Europe's principal tool for those wishing to access data on raw materials.

2. ABOUT THE RAW MATERIAL INFORMATION SYSTEM (RMIS)

The RMIS responds to the need of strengthening the European Union Raw Materials Knowledge Base and acts as the core access point to such expertise and as interface for policy support. They also provide a structured repository of knowledge and support regarding the legislations of EU Community and Member States. In particular, the EC RMIS defines further needs, gaps and recent national legislation updates in the EU Member States. The overarching goal of the RMIS is to facilitate: The availability, coherence and quality of know-how required by specific EU raw materials policies and EC services. The knowledge needs of the EU criticality assessment, the Raw Materials Scoreboard, trade, defense, Circular Economy, due diligence/conflict minerals and other raw materials specific policies. Access to key raw materials information, within and beyond Europe, which complements the know-how currently essential for policy support. Fulfilling the wide range of Union Raw Materials Knowledge Base requires a broad spectrum of different knowledge providers such as national, European and global stakeholders. In addition to satisfying the knowledge needs for policy support within the EC, the RMIS is targeted at providing easy access to structured information to a wide range of stakeholders including the manufacturing industry, extractive industry, recycling industry trade sector, material scientists, economists, academia and education, the wider public, as well as decision/policy makers.

The RMIS aims to support the broad range of EU policy knowledge needs, e.g., the Raw Materials Scoreboard, Critical Raw Materials (CRM) assessment, trade negotiations, and the Material System Analysis (MSA). Various data and information are being collected in the process of developing the policy-related outputs such as the EU CRM assessment, RM Scoreboard, RMIS trade module, and MSA. In general, RMIS covers the following knowledge needs:

- EU raw materials policy.
- Raw materials trade.
- Material efficiency, stocks and flows, recycling.
- Social and environmental sustainability and other information in the wider sense

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3. RMIS GENERAL CONCEPT

According to the proposed concept, a distributed system for processing information about the state of the raw material base of the EU consists of a database server that stores and processes information and remote data sources, which can be all related projects and companies. Data is transferred to the server via the global Internet, while a single interface for all end users is provided by a dedicated server, which will allow data entry into the database without installing specialized software for end users. During this period the emphasis is on the raw material data network in the EU looking at data collection, developments and use. In the parallel the RMIS Goal is dedicated to introducing the detailed results of EU funded projects and guidance for primary and secondary raw materials data. The Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) is an instrument of the European Commission, developed by the Directorate-General (DG) Joint Research Centre (JRC) in cooperation with the DG for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (GROWTH).

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4. RMIS GENERAL STRUCTURE AND DESIGN

The RMIS structure supports the collection, organization, storage and communication of information on raw materials, and to a certain degree on materials, and components and products made of them. The content and some of the functional elements of the website menu at its different levels are going to correspond implicitly with the major EU policy-related drivers e.g. -> Raw Material Initiative (RMI), -> European Innovation

Partnership on Raw Materials (EIP-RM), -> Resource Efficiency, -> Circular Economy, -> Sustainable Development, -> Common Security and Defense. It also includes the raw materials value chain and such aspects as public awareness, education, global information sources, JRC's in-house science and technology services, etc. Website users, including stakeholder groups (EU and Member States decision makers, industry representatives, international and domestic investors, academia (research and education entities) and interested public may have differing interests and foci. To properly address such differing interests, the RMIS has established a flexible system architecture in order to provide the potential functional links among the website menu entries. The following bullets provide a brief overview of the content of the RMIS website as of November 2022 Items by-Items and Figure by Figure →

OVERVIEW & NEWS section is the section provides an overview of the European raw materials context, the policy mandate that underlies the development of the RMIS, its goal and scope and news. The “Overview” also includes a ‘news’ section, as well as present the ‘Knowledge needs’, ensuring users to access information that is divided into the following blocks: Policy driver, Relevant link and Legislation & policy documents. It also provides access to “Terminology” related to e.g. trade, sustainability, indicators, legislation, etc. The Glossary is a combination of legal definitions extracted from the EU Community legislation, and technical definitions which are originating from other international documents. Therefore, the source of the definition is always indicated.

POLICY & LEGISLATION provides current events, information and analysis to support EU legislatures, research on important international public policy issues. The section “EU legislation” provides an overview of the most important policy fields and documents (Commission Communications in most cases) that directly support the development of the RMIS (e.g. the Circular Economy Action Plan) or of the European knowledge base on raw materials (e.g. the European Raw Material Initiative), as well as of those that are anyway relevant in the context of the RMIS development. It will also include an overview of selected relevant international conventions and initiatives, EU Treaties and secondary Community legislation, as well as links to relevant national legislation at the country profiles section.

CRM ANALYSES ON RUSSIA'S AGGRESSION AGAINST UKRAINE includes a series of briefings focused on impact assessments for supply security of key materials. It provides information about potential supply disruption of relevant non-food, non-energy raw materials due to Russia's war against Ukraine, with a snapshot of the present situation, and analyses of the future perspective. For example, Newsletter: Special edition includes five important updates: i) Share of global raw material production in Ukraine, Belarus and Russia, with red triangles indicating the Critical Raw Materials (CRMs), referring to the EC 2021 List of CRMs. Materials with a share of less than 3% are excluded, and the red dots represent the location of the mining sites of Ukrainian raw materials, ii) Russia war against Ukraine: how it will impact EU's security of supply, iii) Key materials and sectors likely to be most affected, including a list critical raw materials are mainly imported from Russia, as well as EU imports from the Russian Federation, Ukraine and Belarus of the NFNE product aggregate, by critical & non-critical materials (total values and percentages), iv) focus on Russia, and v) JRC Technical report addressing Ukraine.

RESILIENCE, AUTONOMY, SECURITY, SECURITY-OF-SUPPLY & CRITICALITY updates

updates on Critical Raw Materials are both of high **Economic Importance** for the EU and have a high **Risk of Supply** disruption described in the section of "What are CRM". It also includes the updated lists of CRM and factsheets from 2011, **Dashboard for**

Critical Raw Materials, reporting on the evolution of the assessment results for all candidate raw materials selected for criticality assessment, **Autonomy** covering external dependencies and vulnerabilities, and the consequent necessity for diversification of domestic and external sources of supply.

Top Fact 1 →

Critical Raw Materials (CRM).

Within the Raw Materials Initiative, particular attention is given to "Critical Raw Materials"(CRMs). 'CRMs' are raw materials of a high importance to the economy of the Union and whose supply is associated with a high risk. Communication on the Raw Materials Initiative is to update the list at least every three years launched in 2011. The purpose of the list is to incentivise the European production of CRMs and facilitate the launching of new mining and recycling activities. The list is also being used to help prioritise needs and actions. For example, it serves as a supporting element when negotiating trade agreements, drafting legislation, challenging trade distortion measures or promoting research and innovation. The list of CRMs serves also as a basis for EU and national policy measures in relation to (critical) raw materials. The latest Commission Communication was in 2020. The 2020 list confirms 26 of the 2017 CRMs. Three CRMs in the 2020 list were not considered as critical in the 2017 list: Bauxite, Lithium and Titanium. Conversely, Helium, critical in the 2017 CRM list, is no longer in 2020. Strontium is the only new candidate material that is in the 2020 list of CRMs.

All raw materials, even when not classed as critical, are important for the EU economy. The fact that a given material is classed as non-critical does not imply that availability and importance to the EU economy can be neglected. Moreover, the availability of new data and possible evolutions in EU and international markets may affect the list in the future.

The full documentation about the 2020 CRMs list can be downloaded as "2020 Study on the review of the EU's list of Critical Raw Materials (2020)" on <https://ec.europa.eu>

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RAW MATERIALS SCOREBOARD & MONITORING includes indicators covering themes and subthemes of the Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe and aims to monitor its implementation, communicate concerning

the link between resources, circular economy and stakeholders. This also presents knowledge from other scoreboards and monitoring systems including the Resource Efficiency Scoreboard, the European Innovation Scoreboard, and the framework of indicators being developed for monitoring progresses towards a more Circular Economy, as well as information regarding the monitoring of the EIP Raw Materials (e.g. Strategic Implementation Plan, annual monitoring reports)

CIRCULAR ECONOMY, SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS & WASTE covers Secondary Raw Materials (SRMs) generation, use, applications, trade, end-of-waste, and any related aspects along the value chain. It emphasises the role and importance of related activities for the supply of raw materials for the EU economy, providing access to knowledge on e.g. data and monitoring indicators of SRMs (e.g. data sources, tools and assessment methods), how SRMs are tackled in the five “priority areas” indicated by the Circular Economy Action Plan (in particular, CRM and construction & demolition), as well as an analysis of SRMs in other specific industry sectors.

ENVIRONMENTAL & SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY describe impact of environmental factors that can be directly affected by the activity of the raw materials sector, such as good health, clean water, affordable and clean energy, and climate action, including certain raw materials that are also essential for the deployment of green, low-carbon and pollution abatement technologies. Social sustainability includes employment issues, SLO, more information about circular economy (CE) that has positive effects in terms of reduced environmental impacts and resources use and other relevant topics.

ECONOMIC & TRADE contains Raw materials trade flows; trade agreements; foreign direct investment stocks and flows; trade performance indicators and trade-related country profiles, as well as US tariffs impact on Aluminium imports. This information also related to trade performance (e.g. import/export of raw materials at country level), global production of primary and secondary raw materials, as well as knowledge on foreign investments, trade promotion and restrictiveness.

FORESIGHT, STRATEGIC VALUE CHAINS & MATERIAL FLOWS helps improve policy design, develop future-proof strategies and ensure that short-term actions are coherent with long-term objectives. The Commission has relied on foresight for many years; it now aims to embed it into all policy areas, to exploit its strategic value. The first Strategic Foresight report highlights, as an example, the important role of raw materials in the geo-political context in relation to resilience and autonomy. In turn Material flow provides an aggregate overview, in thousand tonnes per year, of the material flows into and out of an economy.

EW-MFA covers solid, gaseous, and liquid materials, except for bulk flows of water and air. The RMIS Supply Chain Viewer (SCV). The SCV provides an overview of networks of selected raw materials supply chains, consisting of supplying countries, material products, product applications, and economic sectors using such products and materials.

➤ 4 different view types that enable analyse of various aspects

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- 85 material chains (8 with multiple production stages)
- 133 supplying countries
- 21 NACE-2 economic sectors
- 152 product applications

Top Fact 2 → Foresight studies.

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Future foresight and forward planning is a permanent and major task of all decision makers in the raw material sector in order to ensure the undisrupted supply of economies at all scales. To provide an appropriate background initiated prospective studies primarily on basis of EU H2020|EUROPE consortia, JRC and international entities hereby below.

The European Innovation Partnership on Raw Materials is a stakeholder platform that brings together representatives from industry, public services, academia and NGOs. JRC has a major role in monitoring and assisting its implementation. It plays a central role in the EU's raw materials policy framework:

- via reinforcing the Raw Materials Initiative by translating the strategic policy framework into concrete actions and by mobilizing the stakeholder community to implement them;
- by being instrumental in securing R&I funding: while **Framework Programme 7 (2007-2013) included approximately €180 million** for raw materials R&I, **Horizon 2020 (2014-2020) reserved €600 million** for research on the challenges related to raw materials and **Horizon Europe already positioning the budget ~€300 million only for 2021-2022.**

The EIP's Strategic Implementation Plan (SIP) withal is one of the most important Community documents **on future planning** in the raw material sector by setting out specific objectives and targets. The Strategic Implementation Plan includes **95 Concrete Actions**, structured into **7 Priority Areas** and **24 Action Areas**.

RAW MATERIAL PROFILE covers raw material dashboard, mineral inventory and RM factsheets, regularly updating a list of critical raw materials (CRMs) for the EU and the underlying European Commission (EC) criticality assessment methodology. It also provides insights on the present and past lists of CRMs for the EU, with emphasis on the JRC role to continuously improving the methodology to identify CRMs, as well as a structured and facilitated access to the detailed potentially critical raw materials factsheets. It furthermore provide information on related considerations, such as EIP monitoring and evaluation, circular economy monitoring, resource efficiency scoreboard, EC's resilience dashboard.

COUNTRY PROFILE includes profile of the EU and African countries provides country-specific data and indicators related to non-food, non-energy raw materials. These data and indicators are derived from data from official sources and well-established data providers, or by their elaboration. Each profile is structured into nine thematic sections: i) Key indicators; ii) Investment and regulatory framework; iii) research, development and innovation; iv) Resources and reserves; v) Supply; vi) Raw materials use; vii) Trade; viii) Environment; and ix) Social & Policy. These reports mirror the content of the profiles developed for countries, as available online in the RMIS.

KNOWLEDGE GATEWAY & LIBRARY updates the EU funded projects, EU Science Hub and library, including most relevant terms/concepts used in the raw materials context based on EU legislation, international standards and H2020 consortia's glossaries, an up-to-date searchable library of major reports to be later developed into a metadatabase, as well as a section focused on harmonisation aspects in the RM sector such as harmonisation of RM classification, trade classes, extractive waste facility classes, landfill classes, etc.

Top Fact 3 →

The “Raw Materials in Vehicles”

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The “Raw Materials in Vehicles”

strategic value chains and material flows” section.

The app provides information on:

- the stocks and flows of vehicles placed on the EU market as well as flow of collected and recycled End-of-Life Vehicles (ELV);
- the related stocks and flows of Critical Raw Materials (CRM) and other relevant metals embedded in vehicles.
- the methodological aspects and key references.

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5. RMIS FUN FACTS QUIZ

1. What is needed the European Commission's Raw Materials Information?
Please, choose the incorrect option
 - A. Tool for future development based on Material Flow Analyses updates
 - B. Tool for trade partners, industrial sectors, or products along the supply chain
 - C. Tool for strategy in industrial value chains, supply chain viewer
 - D. All choices are correct
2. What does RMIS «Supply Chain Viewer» offer?
 - A. Assessment the product complexity belonging to various material supply chains
 - B. Underlying graph database technology
 - C. Flexible search of aspects of interest along subsoil use legislation
 - D. All choices are correct
3. What do RMIS «Strategic Industrial Value chains» include?
 - A. Analyses of CRMs in batteries value chains
 - B. Forecast for the security of supply, recycling features, technology dependence
 - C. Facilitation of minerals and land-use policy
 - D. All choices are correct
4. What is the meaning «Critical Raw Materials (CRMs)»?
 - A. Those raw materials that are economically and strategically important
 - B. Those raw materials that have a high-risk associated with their supply
 - C. Mineral resources in sustainable land-use planning
 - D. All choices are correct
5. What shall be done to strengthen Europe's Critical Raw Material Strategy?
 - A. Improve further building the EU knowledge base of primary and secondary raw materials
 - B. Policy-making related to CRMs in general or linked to specific applications or sectors
 - C. Diversification and Substitution
 - D. All choices are correct

Hint: 1. D, 2. C, 3. C, 4. C, 5. D

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6. REFERENCES

1. [RMIS](#)
2. [CRM 2020 CRITICAL](#)
3. [CRM 2020 NON CRITICAL](#)
4. [SCREEN PROJECT](#)